

November 25, 2024

The Formation of a Unified Theory of Political Organizations: An Interdisciplinary Approach to the Analysis, Design, and Improvement of Political Parties

Abstract. The article examines political parties as complex, multidimensional collective agents that require an interdisciplinary approach to their analysis, design, and improvement. It presents the main scientific approaches to the study of political organizations: political, legal, social, organizational, and systemic. The necessity of forming a unified theory of political organizations that integrates concepts from various disciplines based on the organizational approach is emphasized. Four fundamental components of building political parties of the next generation are identified: the type of ideology, the type of organizational agent, the methodology of activity, and the method of collective activity. An approach to political parties as an industrial production aimed at producing governing influences at various levels of management in informational and physical spaces is substantiated. A method of collective activity in a dynamic network of members of different-level subdivisions of political parties is proposed, which adapts their organizational structure to the conditions of the modern postmodern information society. This, in turn, will ensure the stability, coherence, efficiency, and effectiveness of political organizations of the next generation.

Keywords: theory of political organizations, interdisciplinary approach, dynamic network, governing influences, collective activity.

Any political party is a complex multidimensional collective agent. Certain manifestations and aspects of this agent are studied within various scientific disciplines and approaches (scheme 1). At the same time, each of them uses its specific terminology and concepts that are difficult to reconcile with one another.

This complicates the establishment of a unified **theory of political organizations** that would enable the examination and representation of

political parties with a focus on their internal unity, as well as the research, improvement, and design of these organizations.

Scheme 1. Political party as a subject of research in different scientific approaches.

Political parties are traditionally considered within the framework of political party studies, which is a **political science approach** aimed at analyzing political systems and processes. Political party studies examine these organizations as political actors or, in other words, agents characterized by a high level of political participation and competing for power.

At the same time, all political parties are legal entities clearly defined by law, or, in other words, legal agents bound by legislation. They are required to comply with their own statutes and operate exclusively within the legal framework. In this context, they are considered within the framework of the **legal approach**, which examines the legal aspects of their interactions.

Furthermore, every political party is classified as an organization or, to be more specific, as an organizational agent. The processes of political parties' establishment, development, and functioning are analyzed within the **organizational approach**. This approach integrates a wide range of interconnected disciplines, including organizational theory, management theory, industrial production organization, organizational behavior, and more.

In addition, it is obvious that political parties consist of small and large groups of people – their members, whose interaction within these groups is examined across various scientific disciplines, such as sociology, social psychology, sociology of small groups, conflict studies, motivation theory, archetype studies, among others. These disciplines form the **social approach** as a separate category of research. It focuses on the interaction of people in the social environment and their influence on one another.

At the same time, political parties can be viewed as social systems that are traditionally studied within the framework of the **systemic approach**, which aims to study the overall interaction between the elements of these systems. The systemic approach allows for the combination of research results on political parties from all other listed approaches at the micro, meso, and macro levels of these organizations.

Thus, the complexity of developing a unified **theory of political organizations** requires the simultaneous consideration of political parties within various humanities, technical, social, and legal disciplines, as well as establishing interconnections between their ideas about these organizations based on a systemic approach.

Therefore, in what follows, while considering political parties mainly within the framework of organizational, social, and systemic approaches, we will try to reconcile the understanding of these organizations with the traditional view of parties within the political science approach. We will ensure this without violating established statutory norms and without exceeding legal boundaries regulated by the legal approach.

In his book¹, the renowned Ukrainian party scholar and expert Yuriy Shveda provided a comprehensive definition of a political party: "A party is a distinct public political organization that has a specific legal status in the state, whether at the national-autonomous or intergovernmental level. It is an association of individuals voluntarily united by a common set of political views, typically formalized in programmatic documents. Grounded in a specific ideology and organizational structure, while representing ideologically shaped social interests, it seeks active participation in social, political, and state affairs, with the goal of attaining and exercising power within the state."

It is evident that in this case, the aim of acquiring and exercising power, in an ideal scenario, is the realization of the shared political views of these individuals within the scope of their ideology concerning the strategy for developing the state and society across key sectors of public life.

Yuriy Shveda outlined the methods of party organization, identified the factors that make them democratic, and analyzed the challenges of intra-party democracy.

He pointed out that "the way a party is organized and its organizational parameters can – and indeed do – influence its behavior in the electoral and parliamentary-government arena."

At the same time, Yuriy Shveda argued that the challenge of implementing intra-party democracy primarily arises from the insufficient development of the existing internal organization of parties.

Modern partyology, as a component of the political science approach, in our opinion, lacks a sufficient conceptual framework and theoretical-methodological foundation to examine and analyze political parties as organizations. Consequently, it is unable to develop and offer specific organizational and technological mechanisms and tools required for the development of the internal organization of parties.

At the same time, these mechanisms and tools have been extensively studied and developed within the organizational approach for industrial production organizations and business companies.

However, there is a fundamental difference between political parties, on the one hand, and business and production organizations, on the other, which is the lack of a key source of managerial energy in political party leaders, which is defined in the organizational approach² as the ability of managers of business and production organizations to punish and reward their employees by adjusting wages.

Thus, given the fundamental absence of wages for the activity of members of political organizations, the use of the organizational approach allows us to identify one of the main tasks that the theory of political organizations needs to address: to develop and introduce compensatory mechanisms for the absence of the aforementioned key source of managerial energy possessed by managers of business organizations.

In our work³, within the framework of the organizational approach, we have identified four invariant fundamental components of party building that determine the potential for development, efficiency, effectiveness, competitiveness, and viability of these organizations in a complex and turbulent external environment, which is the current postmodern information society.

They are the type of party ideology, the type of organizational agent, the methodology of activity, and the method of collective activity of members of different-level party subdivisions.

Subsequently, within the framework of an interdisciplinary approach, which we assume will form the basis for a unified theory of political organizations, we will establish the principles for selecting these components for political parties of the next generation.

Based on the vision of Ukrainian scholar B. Mizyuk⁴ and considering the described organizational paradigm shifts by J. Gharajedaghi⁵, we have proposed³ our definition of a political party as an organizational political agent. It is an active, multiminded organism of a social model, endowed with sensations, consciousness, and will, capable of self-reproducing over extended periods and able to explore and change the world: adequately perceiving information from both external and internal environments, processing and analyzing it in a rational manner, recognizing its own interests, cyclically performing normative planning for their realization (which involves an open selection of means, tasks, goals, and ideals), and acting purposefully in accordance with the developed and approved plans.

According to B. Mizyuk⁴, normative planning covers strategic planning, supplementing it with the selection and revision of the organization's ideals in the process of changes within its internal and external environments.

This allows us to make the following assumptions about the two fundamental components of building the political parties of the next generation:

1. The methodology of the political parties of the next generation should be the strategic management of external and internal environments, which includes the purposeful implementation of the goals developed during the process of strategic planning.
2. The party ideology of the next generation of political parties should be "living⁶" – capable of evolving and adapting to the conditions of the external and internal environments that are constantly changing.

At the same time, as a result of analyzing successive shifts in understanding the nature of organizations, on the one hand, and the change in the nature of scientific knowledge from an analytical to a systemic approach, J. Gharajedaghi⁵ concluded that the main feature of organizations – multiminded systems of the social model is the ability to simultaneously carry out self-reconstruction and distributed (participative) management.

This allows us to make the following assumptions:

1. The methodology of activity – strategic management of external and internal environments, as well as a set of institutional procedures for changing ideology – should be carried out by a political party with the participation of all members of party subdivisions of the relevant levels and invited non-members of the party, including politicians, experts, businessmen, and activists within the framework of distributed management of these environments.

2. The organizational structure of a political party, in order to ensure its integrity and, at the same time, the ability to carry out self-reconstruction to ensure its interaction with each fragment of the external environment in the appropriate organizational form, should be cyclically variable. This, in turn, should be ensured by the method of collective activity of members of different levels of party subdivisions, which, together with the methodology of activity, fully determines this organizational structure.

At the same time, according to the definition of Yuriy Shveda, a political party aims to acquire and exercise power in the state. Within the context of management theory⁷, this allows us to consider it as a strategic agent that operates within its own management object – the entire society, or, in other words, is distributed within a meta-agent: a reflexive-active self-developing environment.

Meanwhile, we have regarded³ the agency of a political party as an emergent property that arises as a result of and is maintained throughout the course of a set of internal organizational processes. These processes constitute the main political process of the party, encompassing the development, discussion, harmonization, adoption, and approval of decisions. Control over this process determines who holds the real power within the organization⁸.

That is, the agent of a party subdivision at any level will be the individual or individuals who control the decision-making process within it. The indicator by which this agent can be identified is their execution of the main political process in the party subdivision – the process of developing, discussing, harmonizing, adopting, and approving decisions.

This makes it possible to distinguish the task of identifying the real agent of a political party responsible for the main political process. This can be one person (party leader), a small group (leadership core), a large group of fixed size (general meetings, conferences, or congresses), which eventually elect a leader and leadership core for the purpose of their actualization, or a large group capable of numerical growth and able to constitute itself as a collective agent, avoiding the delegation of power to the leader and/or leadership core

by its members. It should be noted that delegation, according to Bourdieu's definition⁹, implies that those who delegate their power function automatically become dependent on those to whom it is delegated.

In view of all this, we have assumed that, in line with the third basic component of building political parties of the next generation, their agent should be a large group of party members and invited non-members capable of numerical growth.

This group does not require the legitimation of their agent through elections, external appointments, or approvals, whose shortcomings Pierre Bourdieu discussed in his work⁹.

A collective agent consisting of a large group, capable of numerical growth without losing its agency and also capable of making decisions in real-time, is legitimate by definition due to its nature. It does not need elected or externally appointed leaders to actualize itself in the intervals between meetings of the large group, as opposed to organizations with the agency of an individual or a small group.

This agent simply appoints its representatives who are responsible for various sectors of social life and/or oversee the implementation of specific projects and simultaneously monitors their activities in real time.

This agent delegates authority and responsibility for the execution of decisions, rather than their development and adoption.

At the same time, the systemic approach¹⁰ states that the external emergent properties of any system are determined by its structure. That is, the emergence, ability for sustainable existence, self-reproduction over time, and effective and efficient activity of an individual or collective organizational agent of any type is determined by the structure of the organization it represents. Simplification of the organizational structure, loss of existing interconnections and/or the emergence of new ones between the elements of a certain structured social system causes degeneration of organizations and, accordingly, their initial agent.

One of the most famous representatives of the organizational approach, H. Mintzberg, defines¹¹ "the structure, or configuration, of organizations simply as the sum total of the ways in which its labor is divided into distinct tasks and then its coordination is achieved among these tasks."

In the work³, we have assumed that the "sum total of the ways" in which the process of collective activity is initially divided into distinct tasks specified in this definition is the methodology of its activity, which is implemented by a

political party in relation to the external and internal environment – society and itself. At the same time, "coordination among these tasks" constitutes the method of collective activity, through which a certain agent of a political party implements this methodology.

Thus, we believe that the methodology of activity and the method of collective activity of party members fully and completely determine the organizational structure of a political party as its structural configuration in terms of H. Mintzberg. It can also be said that these two components of party building fully and completely determine the order (technology) of collective activity of members of party subdivisions, which, together with their structural scheme – the organigram, defines their organizational structure as a structural configuration in terms of H. Mintzberg.

At the same time, G. Morgan argues⁸ that the type of external environment is the primary factor that determines the optimal structure and other key parameters of an organization. The authors of the book "Organizational Theory and Design¹²" support this claim, arguing that in a simple, well-defined external environment, the optimal structure would be a simple linear hierarchical one, accompanied by appropriate competition strategies (involving forced compromises), formal communication systems, an inflexible organizational culture, and routine tasks for employees. Conversely, a turbulent external environment necessitates a shift towards a horizontal structure, with appropriate competitive strategies (focusing on cooperation), an effective system of information exchange, an adaptive organizational culture, and delegation of authority.

Accordingly, the decision-making processes in effective and efficient organizations operating in each of these types of environments, as well as the methods of control over them, will be radically different.

In political parties, which, unlike the business organizations studied by G. Morgan, constitute pure political systems operating in a complex, turbulent, and uncertain external environment, the issue of power, its sources, and control over them becomes particularly significant in the context of ensuring the efficiency and effectiveness of these organizations, preventing their degeneration, fragmentation, and the imposition of external governance. Clearly, this most of all concerns the ability to control the decision-making process. For the sake of preserving the functionality, agency, independence, and unity of the parties, as well as their ability to self-reproduce and stabilize their activity, this process needs to be highly structured, algorithmic, legitimate, and, most importantly, systematically ingrained within their organizational culture.

The above-defined method of collective activity of members of different levels of party subdivisions is designed to ensure this process. At the same time, it can be assumed that this method, as a system-forming component of the organizational structure, should ensure that the structure aligns with the type of external environment in which the organization operates. This environment is the current postmodern information society, characterized by a multiplicity of truths and increasing flows of structured and unstructured information from the outside, which makes it complex, turbulent, unpredictable, and uncertain.

While it was quite easy to identify and select the first three fundamental components of party building for the political parties of the next generation, in selecting the fourth component, we must first determine what should become the point of our influence within political parties, or, in terms of a systemic approach, what should be the point of application of the "lever¹³" as a tool for solving the existing problems of these organizations and what this "lever" should be.

Since any party subdivision is a small or large group of its members, its development is best viewed within the framework of social psychology¹⁴, which identifies six stages of group development: group formation, division of its members into subgroups, conflict, development of norms, cooperation, and dissolution.

Obviously, at the first two stages of group development, participants interact in "equal-to-equal" positions, while at all subsequent stages, they interact in "leader-to-subordinate" positions. Given that, as established above, leaders of political organizations do not possess the main source of power available to managers of business and production organizations – to punish and reward employees by adjusting their wages – we can assume that ordinary party members tend to become passive once their group moves past the conflict stage, at which point all intragroup power is concentrated in the hands of the leaders who emerge victorious from the conflict. In our opinion, it is in this way that Michels's law of oligarchization¹⁵, known in political science, is realized.

Meanwhile, it can be assumed that the conflict itself is a tool of biologically determined ranking of group leaders who purposefully escalate it during the conflict stage to gain leadership. Furthermore, the activation of conflict participants during its escalation occurs at the neurohumoral level¹⁶, indicating the unconscious influence of conflict interaction situations on the behavior of conflict participants.

Within the framework of archetype studies¹⁷, it can be considered that at the stage of conflict in natural conditions, the very unstable cultural archetype of competition tends to shift toward the cultural archetype of confrontation. To prevent such a scenario, it is necessary to purposefully and continuously guide this archetype toward cooperation, ensuring it does not veer into confrontation.

Given this, within the systemic approach¹³, it can be argued that the escalation of conflicts in various subgroups of members of different-level party subdivisions represents the critical point for applying the "lever" to prevent such conflicts.

At the same time, archetype studies¹⁸ suggest that the activation of a particular archetype is triggered by the specific interaction situation in which its participants are involved.

This aligns well with the assertion of the situational perspective¹⁹ in social psychology that a person's behavioral choice is primarily determined by the interaction situations they are involved in and their contexts, rather than by attitudes, values, or beliefs, as argued by the dispositional perspective in social psychology.

Returning to archetype studies, it can be assumed that to maintain the prolonged presence of interaction participants within the cultural archetype of competition and to prevent its shift toward confrontation, it is necessary to purposefully keep the participants of interaction in "equal-to-equal" positions. In such positions, they will consistently generate social energy to initiate and escalate conflict; however, due to the inability to escalate it, this energy will be released in moderate amounts – sufficient for the continuous activation of party members. In other words, this entails creating an inexhaustible source of social energy within different-level party subdivisions directly through the order of collective activity of party members, which continuously reproduces predefined interaction situations.

At the same time, the shift of the cultural archetype of competition toward cooperation can be ensured by channel factors, as understood within the situational perspective¹⁹ of social psychology. These factors are purposefully embedded in the interaction situations of party subdivision members and cyclically reproduced by the order of collective activity in a dynamic network. One such factor, for instance, is the written recording of alternative drafts, objections, comments, additions, and proposals by party members during the process of developing, discussing, harmonizing, and adopting party decisions³.

Returning to G. Mintzberg's definition¹¹ of organizational structure within the organizational approach, which interprets it "simply as the sum total of the ways in which its labor is divided into distinct tasks and then its coordination is achieved among these tasks," we can assume that in organizations it is the structure that causes the continuous reproduction of the corresponding interaction situations and their contexts.

Thus, it can be concluded that it is the organizational structure (or, in the terms of G. Mintzberg, organizational configuration) of the party that determines the behavioral choices of members of different levels of party subdivisions in the process of their interaction. A change in this structure will lead to a change in this behavioral choice.

At the same time, as we have established above, both the organizational structure and the interrelated order of collective activity of members of different-level party subdivisions are fully and completely determined by the methodology of activity and the method of collective activity of members of these subdivisions.

Since the methodology of activity in differently structured organizations may be the same, it can be assumed that only the method of collective activity of the participants in the interaction can become a "lever" in the context of a systemic approach that should be applied to the point of conflict escalation in groups of members of different-level party subdivisions.

In other words, the method of collective activity of members of different-level party subdivisions, which should be selected and implemented by leaders or initiators of the establishment of the political parties of the next generation as a key fundamental component of party building, should reliably prevent the escalation of interpersonal and intergroup conflicts in these subdivisions.

Within the framework of conflictology, there are many approaches and strategies to resolve conflicts in social groups in general and in organizations in particular. For example, F. Glasl²⁰ developed a dynamic model of conflicts, which consists of nine stages divided into three basic levels. At each level, interactions occur according to the principles of "win-win," "win-lose," and "lose-lose."

At different stages of conflict escalation in organizations, F. Glasl suggests progressively stronger strategies: moderating the interaction of its participants, inviting a consultant to assist in the conflict resolution process, applying a social-therapeutic strategy to support this process, using mediation, involving a "third party" in the conflict, and securing the intervention of higher management.

In this context, it is precisely the leader in the organization who has the ability to utilize all the aforementioned strategies. His or her role can radically change at each stage – he or she can serve as a moderator, a consultant, a mediator, or the individual making the final decision.

Clearly, all of the conflict resolution strategies proposed by F. Glasl are unsuitable for use in the subdivisions of political parties, since each strategy presupposes the existence of a manager or leader who can intervene at any level of a political organization by applying the appropriate strategy for conflict resolution, provided that both parties involved recognize his or her right to do so. However, even in the lowest-level subdivisions, it is improbable that interventions by higher-level leaders will be seen as legitimate, or that the conflicting parties will agree with the outcomes. This is associated with the fact that political party leaders lack a critical source of managerial energy – the power to reward or punish their members through changes in financial compensation, as discussed earlier. As a result, members are absolved of any obligations towards the higher leadership, allowing them to leave the organization without hesitation if disagreements arise.

At the same time, the organizational approach involves a number of systemic tools, each of which mitigates conflict escalation in specific ways. Below we present four such tools. In our opinion, their combination into the cohesive method of collective activity of members of different-level party subdivisions will lead to a sustainable synergistic effect in the context of preventing conflict escalation.

The first of these – **the decomposition of goals, tasks and areas of responsibility** – makes it impossible to escalate internal conflicts by dividing a large group into subgroups, each assigned a distinct task or component of the overall goal, along with a corresponding sector of responsibility. We hypothesize that assigning unique tasks to different groups and dividing sectors of responsibility will significantly reduce the likelihood of conflict escalation among these groups and their members.

The second tool – **brainstorming** – aims to prevent the escalation of interpersonal conflicts by forbidding criticism of other group members' ideas during its initial phase. In the absence of criticism, there are no grounds for conflicts to emerge. The subsequent phase of brainstorming is integrated with the initial phase of the following tool – the cross-group method.

The third tool – **the cross-group working method**²¹ – prevents the escalation of interpersonal conflicts among representatives and holders of group decisions from other previously disbanded subgroups. It also prevents

the escalation of potential intergroup conflicts by forcibly dismantling group boundaries, directing participants to different cross-groups at random.

The fourth organizational and technological tool – classical **project management** – prevents the escalation of internal conflicts through the temporary nature of the work of executive and project groups, limited authority of their leaders or coordinators, and cyclical equalization of the statuses of participants in these groups within the horizontal network ordered by the previous tools.

Thus, **the method of collective activity for large groups in a dynamic network** is the result of the integration or combination of all the above organizational and technological tools into a cohesive whole. Its application makes it possible to prevent the escalation of interpersonal and intergroup conflicts in a large group of participants within a self-governing network organized in this manner.

Therefore, the four fundamental components of party building identified on the basis of an interdisciplinary analysis of political parties, which fully determine the potential, development scenarios, efficiency and effectiveness, competitiveness, and capacity of these organizations, are the type of ideology, the type of organization agent, the methodology of activity, and the method of collective activity of members of different-level party subdivisions.

In this context, for the political parties of the next generation, we recommend³ selecting a party ideology of an evolving or adaptive type, the agent of the entire party or its different-level subdivisions – a large group of its members and supporters capable of growing in number, the methodology of activity – strategic management, and the method of collective activity of members of different-level party subdivisions in a dynamic network.

At the same time, it is obvious that the interaction of members of different-level party subdivisions results in the production of a certain outcome of their collective activity. It is best to define exactly what this outcome is, as well as to determine what initial raw materials are necessary for its production, within the framework of the model of a political party as an industrial production. In this model, the organized collective activity of a large group of people results in the creation of the intended finished product from the initial raw materials.

The consideration of political parties as industrial production is not a new idea. For instance, Offerlé views²² political parties as "enterprises of a political nature," whose activities involve "exchanging political values" for "active or passive support." However, this metaphor does not address the internal activities of party members within these "enterprises of a political nature,"

necessitating its reinterpretation and reformulation to encompass the internal interactions of these members within different-level party subdivisions.

Let us consider a political party using the well-known universal metaphor of a black box, into which raw materials, people, and resources enter, and from which the finished product emerges. Within such a model of a political party, we assume that the raw material is the information received from the external environment. The political party, as a governing subsystem of the entire social system, processes this information into a finished product, which, in general terms, can be considered a governing influence.

It is evident that such a governing influence must be exerted by the political party on the parent social system at different levels of governance. This enables its decomposition into a series of governing influences corresponding to the relevant levels of governance. (Here, it is important not to confuse the aforementioned levels of governance in the context of their typology with the structural levels of governance of the social system – central, regional, and local).

In the paper³, we proposed the following classification of different types of governance at their corresponding levels, which involves the production of various types of governing influences by the next-generation political party:

Governance at the conceptual level is achieved both through the development and dissemination of **party ideology** as an independent finished product, and by implementing all other components of governing influence, which are developed based on this **ideology, its goals, principles, and values**.

At the same time, at the moment of the party's establishment and at the beginning of its deployment, the party's initiators may adopt one of the existing varieties of ideology or their hybrid as the initial version. Therefore, this ideology cannot yet be considered a finished product developed by the different-level party subdivisions. However, over time and through the course of party activity, this initial version will continuously evolve due to updates, reconstruction, and the addition of new elements generated by practical party activities. This will result in the gradual transformation of the party's ideology, its goals, principles, and values into a key type of finished product: a governing influence at the conceptual level.

Governance at the strategic level is accomplished through the production of a set of interconnected **development strategies** (strategic development plans) for the country, regions, settlements, and communities. These plans are produced, implemented, adjusted, and updated based on party ideology,

along with its goals, values, and principles. Essentially, this process involves translating an abstract and voluminous ideology, consisting of a complex array of interconnected elements (ideas, hypotheses, concepts, theories, ideals, slogans, political development programs, etc.), into practical actions adapted to the relevant local or regional levels at a specific point in time. This translation results in a concise plan designed to solve specific practical tasks and challenges facing the entire society or its geographically distinct parts at the current stage of their development.

Governance at the organizational-structural level is accomplished by developing and implementing a set of **organizational-structural changes** within the framework of development strategies based on party ideology. These changes ensure the emergence of specific, predefined emergent properties of social systems and determine the activity of their subsystems, as well as the behavioral choices of their members.

Governance at the information level is carried out by different-level party subdivisions through the development of a set of **positions** that cover the entire spectrum of current issues and challenges relevant to society's vital activities and arising in real time. These positions are formed based on development strategies and organizational-structural changes that were previously developed on the basis of the party's ideology. It should be noted that the governance of these developed positions can be classified as reflexive management according to the classification by V. Lepsky⁷.

Governance at the directive level is accomplished through the development of **directives** by different-level party subdivisions, aimed at implementing strategies for development, organizational-structural changes, and positions based on party ideology. The recipients of these directives in the external environment are party members and supporters who have been elected or appointed to leadership roles within relevant governmental bodies or local self-governance. In the internal environment, the directives target leaders and coordinators of executive, project, and process groups. It should be noted that directive governance can be classified as classical management according to V. Lepsky's classification⁷.

Governance at the directive, informational, organizational-structural, strategic, and conceptual levels is conducted within **the information space**, and all components of governing influence developed at these levels are structured information of a certain volume and complexity.

Environmental governance is accomplished in **the physical space** through the dispersal of **trained party members and supporters** – managerial

cadres – who are bearers of the party's ideology, values, and principles, as well as knowledge about the decisions made – the governing influences at all previously mentioned levels of governance. Dispersed in this manner, the trained members and supporters of the party will be capable of disseminating and implementing all other governing influences developed by its different-level subdivisions, as well as carrying out the purposeful gathering of information from the external environment.

Activity-based governance is also accomplished in **the physical space** and encompasses a variety of direct **actions** undertaken by members of party subdivisions independently or within various types of permanent and temporary groups. These actions aim to implement development strategies, organizational and structural changes, positions, or directives developed by these subdivisions based on party ideology.

If the different-level subdivisions of a political party are unable to produce governing influence of the requisite complexity and intensity in the necessary amounts to govern the external environment, they quickly lose competitiveness and come under the external control of more complex organizational agents within this environment – oligarchic clans, special services, or criminal organizations.

The governing influences described above can be considered the main products of party production. At the same time, the auxiliary products of party production are the governing influences produced to enable the self-governance of the internal environment – that is, to implement strategic self-governance by the party. The production of such influences should result in the emergence of a set of necessary emergent properties in political organizations and their different-level subdivisions, which arise in the process of party activity.

These properties can include the emergence of: stable and continuous collective agency of all different-level party subdivisions; conflict-free interaction and sustainable collaboration among members of party subdivisions; growing field of trust and relevant organizational ethics; specific combination of different types of motivations of party subdivision members, which will result in the release of social energy in amounts that are necessary and sufficient to achieve the party's program goals; relevant organizational culture that stabilizes organizational activities; positive selection, leading to the promotion of the most ethical, competent, and qualified party members to positions of state power; numerical growth of different-level party subdivisions without compromising their properties; increasing competence and

comprehensive development of party members and supporters; growing reputation of the organization, etc.

The governing influence produced for the purpose of self-governance of the internal environment includes components across the same levels of governance as previously discussed – conceptual, strategic, organizational-structural, informational, directive, environmental, and activity-based.

The main advantage of the classification we propose is the ability to technologize the production processes of all components of governing influence at the specified levels of governance by different-level party subdivisions, during the implementation of strategic management of the external environment and the self-governance of the internal environment.

Consideration of a political party as an industrial production of governing influences from increasing flows of information from external and internal environments within the scientific discipline "Organization of Industrial Production" enables the detailed development of all organizational parameters of such organizations. These parameters include defining the combination of motivations among members of such political organizations and introducing a motivational tool designed to compensate for the absence of a key source of managerial energy among party leaders, which is possessed by managers of business and production organizations – the ability to punish or reward employees by adjusting their wages.

In the paper³, we have demonstrated that such a tool will be the order (technology) of collective activity of members of different-level party subdivisions, entirely determined by the methodology of activity and the method of collective activity in a dynamic network, selected by their leaders. Its implementation will ensure the emergence of necessary compensators for the lack of material motivation in such organizations. We also assumed that these compensators would be competitive and stroking-evaluative motivations, which belong to the basic level of Maslow's hierarchy²³.

At the same time, the four fundamental components of party building selected within the organizational approach allow us to assume that the political parties of the next generation will be able to deploy in an optimal path in accordance with the Adizes methodology², which prescribes the following sequence of activation of managerial functions: first, the **(I)**ntegration function is activated, followed by the **(V)**isionary function (analogous to the **(E)**ntrepreneurial function of business organizations). Next, the **(A)**dministrative function is activated, and finally, the **(P)**roduction function is activated. This will result in a fundamental change in the properties of the

political parties of the next generation compared to the properties of the existing political parties, which were deployed in a typical path, sequentially activating the **(V)**isionary, **(P)**roduction, **(A)**dministrative, and **(I)**ntegrating functions.

At the same time, ensuring the implementation of the main production process in political parties of the next generation, based on the order of collective activity of members of different-level party subdivisions developed by us, and ensuring impersonal management of all processes within such production requires the introduction of a compound mechanism for coordinating a variable structure – the dynamic network. This mechanism is based on the coordination mechanism of mutual adjustment, which is ordered and reinforced by all other coordination mechanisms identified¹¹ by H. Mintzberg: the standardization of work processes, qualifications, outputs, norms, as well as direct control. In other words, the compound coordinating mechanism of the dynamic network integrates all the coordinating mechanisms identified by H. Mintzberg into a unified whole.

Meanwhile, the only part of an organization with a variable structure – a dynamic network – will be its dynamic operational core, which will function as an expanded meeting of the governing body of a party subdivision at any level. This core, with a semi-permeable border with the external environment, will perform the functions of all other parts of the organization described by H. Mintzberg. To fulfill these functions, it will be capable of restructuring itself at any time, fully or partially, into any organizational structures that will ensure the emergence of the relevant properties necessary to solve problems in external environments of certain types at specific times.

This allows us to assume that the structural configuration we have developed – the dynamic network – is positioned above the hexagon of configurations proposed by H. Mintzberg and is located at the top of an irregular hexagonal pyramid with this hexagon as its base.

Also, in the paper³, we demonstrated that party production can be regarded as a serial, multi-nomenclature, intermittent-flow production of unique yet typologically standardized products – namely, governing influences – within the context of the strategic management of external environments and the strategic self-governance of the party subdivision itself. Furthermore, within this framework, we presented a suitable multi-nomenclature intermittent-flow production line for implementing such production by the different-level subdivisions of political parties of the next generation.

In addition to the systemic prevention of interpersonal and intergroup conflicts within different-level party subdivisions, which will inevitably arise during the interaction of their members, the method of collective activity in a dynamic network developed by us, along with the variable organizational structure of next-generation political parties designed on its basis – the dynamic network – will resolve a number of other fundamental problems related to the functioning of political parties.

Thus, preventing the escalation of internal conflicts will halt the effect of Michels' law of oligarchization¹⁵ within such political parties. The increased degree of organization of political parties, as understood by Eric Berne²⁴, following the implementation of a variable structure – the dynamic network – and the decomposition of the entire scope of these organizations' activities into priority sectors will significantly increase the amount of time that rank-and-file party members can dedicate, on a voluntary basis, to party activities as a result of enhancing their competence and expertise through learning, work, and other activities outside the party. The distribution of internal party power to make decisions through their production, discussion, harmonization, adoption, and approval within large groups of members and non-members of the party will mitigate the risks of direct pressure on party leaders from other organizational agents operating within the same society or externally.

At the same time, the construction of next-generation political parties will address a pressing global issue²⁵: the devaluation of expert knowledge and the relegation of its bearers to the same level as anyone expressing an opinion on the same topic in the mass media or social networks. With the establishment of such parties, decisions proposed by experts will become party decisions, the implementation of which will be institutionally supported by the entire organization. This will inevitably elevate the significance of expert knowledge and ensure the leading role of experts in the activities of political parties and in society itself.

Thus, the utilization of an interdisciplinary approach to the analysis of political parties allows for the technologization of the activities of members of their different-level subdivisions, the development of appropriate tools to motivate these members in order to compensate for their lack of material motivation, and to ensure the production of governing influences of appropriate complexity and intensity within a given timeframe, establishing each step of their production and the tools for monitoring the implementation of these steps.

At the same time, it can be assumed that the formation of a unified **theory of political organizations**, which would allow us to consider and represent

political parties in terms of their internal unity, as well as to research, improve, and design these organizations, is possible only within the framework of an interdisciplinary approach that would be able to combine a number of humanitarian, technical, social, and legal disciplines, establishing interconnections between their perspectives on these organizations based on a systemic approach.

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